

The impact leadership has on operational readiness. A case study of a British Army Attack Aviation Regiment.

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Executive Summary

This research project examines the role leadership plays in enhancing operational readiness and uses a British Army Attack Aviation Regiment as a case study. Due to leadership and operational readiness being such broad topics, the research is supported by objectives that include: the influence leadership has on personnel readiness, the role leadership plays in maintaining equipment readiness and the relationship between leadership and training readiness. The research methodology was qualitative in nature and used semi-structured interviews on a cross section of Regimental personnel to gather primary data. A second source of primary data, in the form of written directives, was used as a form of triangulation to verify the findings. Academic literature, military leadership and military readiness doctrine provided a strong foundation for the theory. The unit was preparing for and deployed to Eastern Europe during the research period. The findings from this live operational deployment revealed that leadership is a critical enabler of all aspects of operational readiness in this high-performance and high-risk organisation. The evidence suggests that clear direction and aligned priorities influence how the Regiment prepares for operations. Personnel readiness and resilience is established and maintained by challenging and supporting people. Aircraft serviceability and aircrew training are central to mission execution, but collaborative and realistic training enhances operational readiness. Communication and tempo of operations arise as unexpected themes and are also addressed. The author contributes to knowledge by introducing the concept of “leadership driven readiness,” which builds upon and adapts the Army Leadership Code and other academic leadership theories. The concept provides recommendations on how leadership practices can enhance operational readiness within high-performance and high-risk units. This research project contributes to knowledge by highlighting the link between leadership and operational readiness in a demanding and highly specialised unit.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the effectiveness of Army units, particularly high performance, high tempo units that are held at high readiness. Readiness is a scaled period that is measured in hours or days to enable an effective response to an unknown crisis. High readiness forces' readiness states can range from extremely high readiness (minutes to 48 hours' notice to move) to high readiness (30 days' notice to move (JDP 0-01, 2022)). Operational readiness consists of a process known as force generation, which is providing suitably trained and equipped forces for an immediate operational deployment to an unknown crisis (JDP 0-01, 2022). Ongoing conflicts around the world demonstrate the lack of stability and peace. These global disruptions highlight a paradox that is widely attributed to General Carl von Clausewitz "*To secure peace is to prepare for war,*" which emphasises the importance of preparedness in order to deter hostile actions (von Clausewitz, 1997). Attack Aviation Regiments provide Apache AH-64E helicopters which are battle winning capabilities that offer versatile and decisive effects across a wide range of operations (JDP 0-30, 2022). These effects include but are not limited to unmatched precision and firepower, rapid response and manoeuvrability, reconnaissance and target acquisition. Having these capabilities means that Attack Aviation Regiments have specific readiness responsibilities and leadership of all levels have a direct impact on the effectiveness of the unit.

1.2 Interest

The author is a Commissioned Officer in the British Army and has extensive leadership experience that ranges from the tactical level, up to the strategic level. Currently serving as a Squadron Second in Command within an Attack Aviation Regiment, he is directly responsible for maintaining and enhancing operation effectiveness within a unit held at very high readiness. Having served in a number of command and leadership roles, the author has developed a keen interest in understanding and contributing towards how better leadership can contribute to operational readiness.

1.3 Research Gap

There are vast amounts of existing literature on leadership and operational readiness individually, but there are few studies which address and intersect these functional areas, specifically within Attack Aviation. This creates a large gap of knowledge within a unique aviation sector that highlights the challenges faced by high tempo Attack Aviation Regiments. The Apache AH-64E is an extremely advanced aircraft. It is equipped with sophisticated sensors, avionics and highly

technical combat systems (Gilmore, 2014) that must have highly skilled operators. Due to the logistical burden presented by the aircraft and its associated equipment, sustaining the serviceability and readiness of the platforms requires strong leadership, especially during deployments. Military aviation is governed differently from civilian aviation and requires well-informed leadership (JDP 0-30, 2022; Director Military Aviation Authority, 2024). The strategic decision-making process within attack aviation sometimes involves complicated command structures that can integrate joint forces and multinational coalitions. Due to these challenges, understanding how leadership influences personnel, equipment and training readiness within attack aviation remains an unexplored but important area of research.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

This research project will examine the impact leadership has on operational readiness by analysing how different leadership styles affect personnel, equipment and training readiness. The aim is supported by the following research objectives (RO):

RO1. Examine the impact of leadership styles on operational readiness.

RO2. Assess the influence of leadership on personnel readiness.

RO3. Evaluate the role leadership plays in maintaining equipment readiness.

RO4. Examine the relationship between leadership and training readiness.

RO5. Provide recommendations on how leadership practices enhance operational readiness.

1.5 Significance and Contribution

The author aims to contribute to military and academic leadership literature by highlighting the role that leadership plays in establishing, maintaining and developing operational readiness. By bridging the gap between leadership and operational readiness theories, this research offers recommendations to enhance personnel, equipment and training readiness to specialised units. The findings serve as references for leadership training and operational readiness management for military leaders and policy makers on strategies to optimise leadership effectiveness within units that are continuously held at very high readiness. This research project also identifies leadership challenges that are unique to Attack Aviation and provides recommendations to overcome them to sustain operational readiness.

1.6 Chapter Synopsis

This chapter outlines the background of the project and highlights the gap in knowledge. The Literature Review introduces fighting power and examines leadership theories and operational

readiness frameworks by using existing research on both topics. The third chapter describes the research approach and data collection methods as well as ethical considerations. Chapter 4 reports and presents the research data by explaining and evidencing how leadership impacts readiness within the Regiment. The Discussion Chapter interprets the research findings in relation to the literature review and builds upon existing theories. Chapter 6 provides the key findings, answers the research aim and objectives and demonstrates how this research project is contributing to knowledge. Recommendations for further research are also provided. The final chapter reflects on the author's personal experience in conducting the research project, what was learned and how the MBA competencies were achieved.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this literature review is to develop a comprehensive understanding of how leadership impacts operational readiness within an Attack Aviation Regiment. It will concentrate on existing theories and frameworks from military doctrine and existing academic studies. It will begin with a brief explanation of fighting power before moving on to examining leadership theories that are common within the British Army, focusing predominantly on the transformational, transactional, servant and laissez-faire leadership styles. Case studies of leadership styles within the aviation industry are analysed and operational readiness components and frameworks are examined. This chapter will conclude with a summary of the existing literature.

2.2 Fighting Power

Attack Aviation Regiments have specific readiness responsibilities. The equipment they provide is vital to mission success and their operators must be highly skilled and require technical proficiency, they have rapid response capabilities and are held at very high readiness. To understand operational readiness, it is important to know how the Army uses its capabilities and applies fighting power, see figure 1 below. Fighting power dictates the Army's ability to operate and fight wars (JDP 0-01, 2022).

Figure 1: The Components of Fighting Power (JDP 0-01, 2022).

Fighting power consists of three components that enables the Army's ability to operate and fight and consists of the moral component (the will to fight), the physical component (the means to fight)

and the conceptual component (the thought process). Each component mutually supports the other (JDP 0-01, 2022). The components of fighting power have now been established; the next section will examine how leadership acts as a force multiplier.

2.3 Leadership

Leadership is one of the most examined human behaviours, yet it remains one of the least understood phenomena on earth (Burns, 1978, p. 2). The British Army defines leadership as: “A combination of character, knowledge and action that inspires others to succeed.” (Director Leadership, 2021). The core purpose of any Army’s leadership is to get the job done (Ulmer, 2010). Together, these statements highlight the importance of personal qualities and practical application of leadership to achieve a common goal, the mission. The Army Leadership Code (ALC) describes the behaviours which the Army demands its leaders to demonstrate (Director Leadership, 2021). The ALC states that leaders must display the defined behaviours and moral courage to do the right thing. This concept is supported by (Greenleaf, 2002) and (Burns, 1978, p.74), who both state that strong values and being responsible are fundamental to leaders always conducting themselves in an ethical manner. The ALC is made up of seven leadership behaviours, which are defined by the acronym LEADERS: lead by example, encourage thinking, apply reward and discipline, demand high performance, encourage confidence in the team, recognise individual strengths and weaknesses and strive for team goals (Director Leadership, 2021).

In 1978 James MacGregor Burns proposed that transformational and transactional leadership could be understood as a single scale. With transformational leadership sitting at one end, focusing on inspiring change and transactional leadership at the other end and being based on structure and reward (Burns, 1978, p. 4, 19-20). An effective leader must apply the principles of the ALC along with their personality, skills and experience to create a unique leadership style that reflects who they are (Director Leadership, 2021). Studies on the Full Range Leadership Model by Bass and Avolio (1994) suggest that leaders that blend transactional and transformational approaches can greatly improve their own performance as well as their organisations. They go on to reinforce that the Full Range Leadership Model highlights that strong leaders use a mix of styles and adapt them based on what the situation demands. This approach is essential within military environments, where leaders must inspire and direct their teams through crisis situations in order to achieve results (Avolio and Bass, 2001).

Professor John Adair’s Action Centred Leadership theory describes the three key elements of leadership as: individual development, team cohesion and achieving the task. Adair describes the elements as independent and mutually supporting, where each component overlaps and influences the others in a constantly shifting dynamic (Adair, 2009). It is acknowledged that it is difficult to

balance all three elements at the same time and leaders must balance this tension to maintain effectiveness (Adair, 2009; Director Leadership, 2021).

Ubuntu leadership and the Army's Diversity, Inclusion and Behaviours Policy highlight the importance of diverse and inclusive teams to improve problem solving (Army Headquarters, 2021). Ubuntu's philosophy of inclusive leadership by embracing a culture of community spirit and shared goals aligns with the Army's aim of valuing a wide range of backgrounds and experiences (Ncube, 2010). Having people with different experience and a diversity in education and background makes a team stronger. It helps the team adapt and encourages innovation (Ncube, 2010; Army Headquarters, 2021). General leadership theories have now been explored; the transformational leadership style is next to be examined.

2.4 Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a method where leaders and followers motivate and inspire each other to grow and succeed (Burns, 1978, p. 4). This leader and follower dynamic is influenced by the way they interact (Bass et al., 2003) because every situation provides opportunity for the relationship to grow. Avolio et al., 1991) developed the framework of the transformational leadership's Four I's, which includes: idealised influence (leaders act as role models), inspirational motivation (articulating a compelling vision), intellectual stimulation (challenge followers to think and innovate) and individualised consideration (support and development). Lieutenant General Ulmer indicates that the characteristics and behaviours demonstrated by transformational leaders are often unnoticed by superiors but are clearly visible to subordinates and peers (Ulmer 2010). He argues that superiors are focused on the measurable outputs, such as getting the job done and following direction. Ulmer (2010) suggests that these immediate results may explain why the Army excels at producing the most effective short-term managers while also producing the largest number of true leaders on the planet.

Simon Sinek's Golden Circle of "why", "how" and "what" aligns with transformational leadership through its emphasis on purpose and inspiration. Sinek's model states that we must start with the "why", this inspires subordinates to connect their efforts to the vision, which is a key component of transformational leadership (Bass et al., 2003; Sinek, 2011, p 49-59) that provides trust and commitment (Eaton et al., 2024). The Socratic Method which refers to "*disciplined questioning that can be used to pursue thought in many directions and for many purposes*" (Paul and Elder, 2007), compliments Sinek's concept by encouraging deeper thought by asking probing questions such as "why", "how" and "what". This disciplined questioning technique supports the philosophy of transformational leadership by encouraging motivation and articulating organisational vision (Paul and Elder, 2007).

Some academics view transformational leadership negatively. Tourish and Pinnington (2002) argue that it creates cult like behaviours. They suggest that cultish organisations are usually led by charismatic leaders that have compelling visions and subordinates are encouraged to believe their leader has their own best interests at heart. Eaton et al., (2024) propose that charisma can have a negative impact on empowering followers, which results in a dynamic where the followers must do as they are told without the means of providing feedback. In these situations, followers are rewarded for obedience and are penalised for any dissent or disagreement. Tourish and Pinnington (2002) criticise Bass' concept of idealised influence and suggest this cult-like behaviour suppresses independent thought. Burns (1978, p. 247) did not consider charisma as essential to transformational leadership, and Tourish and Pinnington (2002) and Eaton et al. (2024) note that he was cautious of charismatic leaders with an idealised influence for this very reason. To balance the views on leadership, the next section will focus on the transactional leadership which is often employed within the Army.

2.5 Transactional Leadership

Burns (1978, p.19-20) defines transactional leadership as an “*exchange of valued things*”. He notes that leader and follower recognise each other's power, attitudes and needs. The connection between them is temporary and focused on an exchange that does not involve a shared goal or purpose. This principle of exchange is supported by Bass et al., (2003) when they state that followers obey the leader's orders in return for rewards and to avoid disciplinary action. The relationship is backed by a clear and defined chain of command where subordinates understand their roles and responsibilities. Transactional leaders are skilled at planning, solving problems and producing results (Tavanti, 2008). This style of leadership is based on setting clear expectations and applying reward when goals are achieved (Avolio et al., 1985; Director Leadership, 2021). The transactional leadership style can also take corrective forms. Active management by exception is when leaders monitor for mistakes then address the problems when they happen (Bass et al., 2003). While the passive-avoidant style is caused when leaders fail to clarify expectations and do not intervene until problems become unavoidable (Bass et al., 2003). Although transactional leadership can clarify goals and establish order, Bass (1990) argues that it can lead to mediocre performance where subordinates aim to achieve the minimum standard rather than striving for excellence.

Transactional leadership relies on a hierarchical structure and strict supervision. Innovation and creativity are limited because the focus is primarily on compliance, rather than commitment to achieving a common goal (Avolio and Bass, 2001; Bass et al., 2003). According to Bass (1990), the direct and efficient nature of transactional leadership is good for achieving short term goals and

during crisis management. This makes transactional leadership suitable for military operations or organisations that prioritise structure and the adherence to rules (Tavanti, 2008). Transactional leadership plays a critical role in achieving objectives and maintaining stability within an organisation. Its effectiveness is dependent on the context and the leader's ability to balance reward and discipline and followers working within the framework of exchange relationships (Tavanti, 2008; Director Leadership, 2021). The next section looks at servant leadership where leaders prioritise other people's needs.

2.6 Servant Leadership

Servant leaders are servants first. Greenleaf (2008) emphasised that servant leadership focuses on helping others succeed and highlights the leaders' moral conscience through sacrifice and commitment to a higher purpose with ethical integrity. Greenleaf's (2008) question "*What are you trying to do?*" mirrors Sinek's (2011) Golden Circle concept by encouraging leaders to focus on their purpose or "why". This question highlights the importance of prioritising other people's needs and aligning it with a higher purpose. Servant leadership thrives on paradoxes like leading by serving and solving problems by asking questions (McGee-Cooper et al., 2001). These contradictions empower subordinates and encourage teamwork to solve problems. They also compliment Sinek's (2011) theory of purposeful inquiry which states that reflective and inclusive leadership will drive success (Director Leadership, 2021; Army Headquarters, 2021).

Bernard Bass distinguishes servant leaders from transformational leaders by emphasising that servant leaders focus on meeting the needs of others as their primary goal, while transformational leaders focus on aligning their own needs with others' interests. The values of servant leadership closely align with the Army concept of Mission Command, which emphasises trust, empowerment and decentralised decision making (Greenleaf, 2002; JDP 0-01, 2022). The philosophy of Mission Command combines distributed and complexity leadership to promote adaptability in challenging environments (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007; Konradt, 2014; Jamon J., 2023). Servant leadership empowers teams to collaborate in creating a shared vision. Greenleaf (2008) suggests that effective leaders guide others with clarity and purpose. This aligns with Sinek's (2011) "why" philosophy which emphasises serving others to create a strong culture that encourages trust, loyalty and shared success. The next leadership style to be examined is laissez-faire, this style is sometimes criticised because of the lack of direction.

2.7 Laissez-Faire Leadership

Laissez-faire leaders are characterised by a hands-off approach style of leadership that fails to use incentives or positive reinforcement for their subordinates (Wang et al., 2023). They often neglect

establishing expectations and delay decision making and ignore problems (Wang et al., 2023). Laissez-faire leadership is sometimes criticised. Mokhtar and Yunus (2023) raised concerns about the lack of direction and argue that it causes confusion which can result in poor productivity. Research by Ågotnes et al., (2021) links laissez-faire leadership to low levels of job satisfaction and poor performance because it makes employees feel undervalued. Laissez-faire leadership in the military has also been criticised by Michelson (2013) for its reliance on leaders to develop moral character without structured guidance. Colonel Michelson (2013) argues that the lack of a structure in laissez-faire leadership weakens the leaders' ability to uphold the Army's standards. He states that a proactive approach must be adopted to develop the character of future leaders and training them how to handle ambiguous situations. While laissez-faire leadership is often criticised, Yang (2015) highlights that this approach can have benefits depending on how it is received. Yang (2015) proposes that a lack of involved leadership can be viewed as supporting autonomy to provide freedom and self-control. The next section will explore how leadership is employed within the high-performance aviation sector.

2.8 Leadership in Aviation

The aviation industry is a high pressure and high-performance environment where strong leadership is critical because it influences safety and has a direct impact on operational readiness (Osman et al., 2021). Research by Osman et al., (2021) used the Delphi Hierarchy Process to identify leadership as the most important factor for achieving operational excellence in the Sudanese aviation industry. The researchers stated that leadership was the most influential factor, ahead of people management, improvement, operational planning, asset optimisation.

Safety is paramount in aviation and a study by Bastola (2020) that explored the Nepali airline industry found that transformational leadership was the most positive contributing factor to the safety culture. Intellectual stimulation and individualised consideration were highlighted as positive components, which aligns with Avolio et al.'s. (1991) Four I's of Transformational Leadership. A research paper by Ayiei et al., (2020) highlights the connection between leadership and operational airworthiness. The research states that setting objectives and visionary leadership contributes to operational effectiveness. Professional development, training and robust risk management were highlighted as key aspects that maintain aviation safety (Ayiei et al., 2020). Previous tragedies stress the importance of leadership within the aviation industry. The catastrophic loss of RAF Nimrod XV230 in 2006 in Afghanistan highlighted failures in leadership and safety culture with the tragic loss of all fourteen service personnel on board (Haddon-Cave, 2009). Hon Sir Charles Haddon-Cave stated that the "*the first priority for a successful safety culture is leadership*" (Haddon-Cave, 2009).

Applying servant leadership within demanding environments like the aviation industry has been shown to provide positive results on workforce satisfaction and retention. Mirah Berliandari et al., (2024) found that using this leadership style within the Jordanian aviation industry promotes empowerment and commitment, but interestingly, they conclude that the evidence of the effects of this leadership style within military education remains unclear. McGee-Cooper et al., (2001) conducted a study on Southwest Airlines, an American company that prides itself on its distinctive culture which is focussed on servant leadership. The analysis found that they promoted growth and trust through six core practices, including: listening without judgement, being authentic, building a community, power sharing, helping people grow and working together to create a vision. Attention will now turn to the broader concepts of operational readiness.

2.9 Operational Readiness

Operational readiness is defined as:

The period measured from an initiation order to the moment when the headquarters or unit is ready to perform its task from its peacetime location (permanent or forward deployed) or ready for deployment. (JDP 0-01, 2022).

Readiness is complimented by notice to effect (NTE), which refers to the time a unit is given to prepare, travel to its mission location and deliver the desired effect with agreed capabilities. Since NTE is situationally specific and cannot always be planned, units are not usually held at a defined NTE period (JDP 0-01, 2022). According to Paynter (2022), operational readiness represents a state of preparedness which has four foundational pillars: personnel, training, equipment and leadership. The Ministry of Defence (2015) refines readiness into categories such as ready for what, ready for when and what needs to be ready. These dimensions underline the diverse situations Army units may encounter and the importance of mission specific planning. Modern readiness strategies include building resilience to increase the ability to adapt to challenges and stay effective. This is especially important in rapidly changing environments (Børge Brende, 2022).

Herrera (2020) states that operational readiness is made up of three key stages: (1) Building initial readiness: This involves basic training and resource allocation to enable soldiers to continue to more complex training scenarios. (2) Increasing readiness: This is the advancement of individual and collective training to qualify the workforce to deploy on operations with the correct equipment. (3) Maintaining readiness: This includes continuous training and equipping of the unit to enable redeployments on future operations. Figure 2 provides an illustration of the many operational readiness factors. It provides a visual aid of how personnel, equipment and training all feed into readiness as a whole.

Figure 2: Operational Readiness Factors (Herrera, 2020).

2.10 Personnel Readiness

Operational readiness also means having sufficiently trained personnel within the unit to be able to carry out the mission (Herrera, 2020). These people must have the right mindset and a willingness to learn and adapt. Leaders must be able to adapt their style to inspire and guide their teams through challenging circumstances (Avolio and Bass, 2001). They must demonstrate crisis and emotional leadership, which according to Jin et al. (2024), is regarded as the best mentality to have when managing crisis situations. According to Pendleton (2019), maintaining readiness depends on the careful management of the workforce tempo. Pendleton (2019) also reported that high tempos with numerous deployments has a negative effect on personnel wellbeing and overall Army readiness. This is even more relevant within Brigade Combat Teams and Combat Aviation Brigades (Pendleton, 2019). These challenges highlight the importance of balance and the careful management of personnel. Herrera (2020) provides a metrics framework to assess personnel readiness levels. These include the proportion of deployable people compared to the authorised numbers. These metrics confirm units are adequately staffed and the individuals are skilled and prepared to carry out their responsibilities (Herrera 2020). The next section explores equipment readiness and how it drives operational effectiveness.

2.11 Equipment Readiness

Confidence in the equipment provides morale and cohesion which leads to an increase in fighting spirit (JDP 0-01, 2022). Equipment readiness, also referred to as “serviceability”, is how functional a unit’s equipment is. A unit held at readiness could hold all its allocated equipment but suffer from poor readiness statistics if the equipment is not serviceable. Equipment readiness is measured by calculating the percentage of the unit’s equipment that is designated as mission essential against the equipment that is mission capable and able to deploy. This measurement can sometimes be impacted by the availability of spare parts, planned maintenance and insufficient budgets. Workforce shortages, particularly engineers and supply specialists, can cause delays to the maintenance schedule and supply chain (Herrera, 2020).

Air power is extremely important in military operations. It provides speed, reach and precision that influences the battlefield (JDP 0-30, 2022). Apache AH-64E helicopters can deliver this significant power but the platforms are heavily reliant upon time consuming maintenance. The serviceability of equipment depends on having correctly trained personnel to operate and maintain it effectively (Docherty-Hughes & Scottish, 2024). Maintaining state of the art equipment requires the integration of technical maintenance with skilled personnel and robust procedures (Kingston-Howlett et al., 2016). Pendleton (2019) highlights how delays in the maintenance periods for the Patriot Missile System limited training opportunities that had a negative impact on readiness. Pendleton (2019) recommends that the effective management of equipment maintenance would help the Army refocus on readiness. We will now move onto training readiness.

2.12 Training Readiness

Units held at readiness can sustain and increase readiness through a combination of training, field exercises and preparing for rapid deployments. Unlike personnel or equipment readiness, training readiness is more difficult to measure and relies on the commanders’ judgement (Herrera, 2020). Commanding Officers assess how well the unit performs during deployments and field exercises, but the quality of the training varies and depends on how often the unit trains, availability of resources and the types of training or exercises conducted. Recent operational deployments can provide the commander a more accurate picture of their unit’s training readiness (Herrera, 2020).

Past lessons from World War II demonstrate how the relationship between training and operational readiness is important for commanders at all levels (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). General W DePuy of the United States Army witnessed devastating losses during his time in Normandy, DePuy’s division lost 100 percent of its enlisted men and 150 percent of its officers within six weeks (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). These losses provided him with a lesson on the consequences of poor

training and leadership, and this experience shaped his career to focus on developing leaders by concentrating on training and education (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). DePuy recognised the link between the “what” and the “how” with training and the “why” and the “whether” to education (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). These links are closely aligned with Sinek’s (2011) Golden Circle and demonstrate that a performance driven training environment is essential for achieving operational readiness.

The war between Ukraine and Russia is a more recent example that highlights how training must be adapted to meet the changing characteristics of war (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). The use of drones and other intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance (ISR) systems have redefined how wars are fought. Traditional skills must not be forgotten, but training on emerging technologies must be integrated to meet the demand of the rapidly evolving tech-driven battlefield (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). A study by Shmelova et al., (2023) proposes that integrating collaborative decision making into aviation training improves safety and communication. Joint training between pilots and other aviation specialists enhances situational awareness and teamwork by enabling the understanding of each other’s roles. They suggest that training with combined resources within a shared environment will reduce errors and improve decision-making. Leadership literature and the components of readiness have been explored; the next section will define the terms that will be used throughout this research project.

2.13 Definable Terms

The tables below act as an analytical lens and provide the definable terms used throughout the research project. Table 1 outlines the leadership styles and provides conceptual clarity on how each style impacts the components of operational readiness. These concepts also form the a priori themes for analysis in the Methodology Chapter.

Table 1: Leadership Definable Terms

Concept	Definition
Transformational Leadership	Inspires and motivates people through vision, innovation and personal development.
Transactional Leadership	Relies on a transaction that is based on rewards and discipline to maintain efficiency, structure and compliance.
Servant Leadership	Prioritises the needs of the team to create trust and support.
Laissez-faire Leadership	Provides autonomy with little supervision but relies on a skilled and well-motivated team.

Table 2 defines the components of operational readiness and provides conceptual clarity on how readiness is understood throughout the research project. Along with Table 1, these concepts will also form the a priori themes for analysis in the Methodology Chapter.

Table 2: Readiness Definable Terms

Concept	Definition
Operational Readiness	“The period measured from an initiation order to the moment when the headquarters or unit is ready to perform its task from its peacetime location (permanent or forward deployed) or ready for deployment.” (JDP 0-01, 2022),
Personnel Readiness	The physical, mental and professional preparedness of personnel to meet operational demands.
Equipment Readiness	The serviceability, availability and maintenance of equipment to support operations.
Training Readiness	The level of collective and individual preparedness through structured training to execute missions.

2.14 Summary

The review of this literature highlights how leadership plays a significant role in shaping operational readiness, particularly attention was drawn to the areas of personnel, equipment and training. The current state of knowledge suggests that transformational leadership provides structure, motivation and inspiration. Transactional leadership offers a hierarchical structure that is accompanied by supervision and compliance, which can be well-suited to some military operations, particularly during a crisis. Servant leadership is focused on meeting the needs of others and is closely aligned with the Army’s concept of mission command which promotes adaptability and decentralised decision making. The hands-off laissez-faire leadership style can cause confusion and decreased productivity due to the lack of vision and clear direction. While there are vast amounts of existing literature on leadership and operational readiness individually, there are few studies which address and intersect these functional areas, specifically within Attack Aviation. The next chapter will explore how leadership and operational readiness can be observed in combination within a live operational deployment.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology used to investigate how leadership impacts operational readiness within an Attack Aviation Regiment. It will include the meta-theoretical assumptions and explain the author's theoretical stance. Details of the sampling strategy will be provided as well as how participants were recruited for the semi-structured interviews. A priori themes provide a focus for how the analysis on leadership and operational readiness was conducted and the use of a second source of primary data is outlined to demonstrate how triangulation was used to verify the findings. Ethical considerations and limitations of the research are discussed before concluding with a summary of the methodological approach.

3.2 Meta-theoretical Assumptions

Meta-theoretical assumptions relate to the beliefs and assumptions that are made when developing or contributing to knowledge (Saunders et al., 2016, p 124). These assumptions include human knowledge (epistemology), the realities of nature (ontology) and the values and ethics (axiology) within the research process (Saunders et al., 2016, p 124). Ontological assumptions can be split into two categories, objective and subjective. An objective view means seeing something as a solid object that can be measured and tested in the same way, no matter who measures or tests it (O'Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 56). The outcome will be the same. A subjective view would see reality shaped by personal experiences and perceptions (O'Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 56). A subjective point of view recognises that everyone has their own perspective, and that knowledge and truth can vary from person to person (Saunders et al., 2016, p 130). The chosen ontological position for this research is one that blends elements of relativism and realism. This position accepts that leadership and readiness exist as tangible components of the Army and fall into the realism category (Saunders et al., 2016, p 127-129). It also identifies that the lived experience of individuals and the way they interpret situations is different, this is categorised as relativism (Levers, 2013; Saunders et al., 2016, p 129).

Epistemology is the study of knowledge, what knowledge is, how we know what we know and how we validate what we know (O'Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 59). A social constructivist epistemology is used throughout this study. This approach allows knowledge to be constructed through social interactions (Saunders et al., 2016, p 130). Concepts such as leadership and operational readiness are not fixed objective measurements; they are seen as subjective perceptions of an individual. These perceptions can be influenced by things such as rank, trade and professional experience (Saunders et al., 2016, p 130). This stance aligns with the qualitative

nature of the study and enables the researcher to explore these perceptions through semi-structured interviews. Axiology is about the role that values and ethics play in research (Saunders et al., 2016, p 128). The researcher had to think about how their own personal values and those of the participants affected the research choices, and the processes applied (Saunders et al., 2016, p 128).

3.3 Theoretical Stance

Interpretivism is a way of understanding social sciences through focusing on human behaviour and experiences (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 65). This research philosophy acknowledges that research is shaped by the way in which the researcher and the participant interact with each other (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 58). In contrast, positivism prioritises objective measurements and the facts (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 56). The beliefs and interpretations of the researcher play a role in how they understand the topic (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 65). Interpretivism accepts that people have different perspectives which creates multiple realities (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 65). Saunders et al., (2016, p 140-141) expand on this by highlighting the richness and complexity of human experiences. They argue that turning real experiences into generalised principles will lose important details. They also emphasise that interpretivism highlights the perspectives of different people. Therefore, the researcher must take an empathetic stance to understand different people’s points of view.

3.4 Research Aim and Objectives

As a reminder, this research project will examine the impact leadership has on operational readiness by analysing how different leadership styles affect personnel, equipment and training readiness. The aim is supported by the following research objectives:

- RO1. Examine the impact of leadership styles on operational readiness.
- RO2. Assess the influence of leadership on personnel readiness.
- RO3. Evaluate the role leadership plays in maintaining equipment readiness.
- RO4. Examine the relationship between leadership and training readiness.
- RO5. Provide recommendations on how leadership practices enhance operational readiness.

3.5 Research Design and Approach

The research design is usually shaped by using established theories and approaches (Saunders et al., 2016, p 162). Although this is not a strict rule, it is important for the researcher to understand and be able to justify their chosen approach (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 52). By doing this,

the researcher can validate their reasoning and methodology (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 52). A well-structured design is important because it ensures that the study follows a logical sequence, and all aspects are logically connected. This demonstrates that the approach is well thought out and the aims or objectives of the study are achieved (Saunders et al., 2016, p 163).

Deciding between quantitative and qualitative research is an important part of the design process. The selection will determine how the data is collected and analysed in order to meet the aim and objectives of the study. Quantitative methods generally focus on numerical data to examine the relationship between variables such as surveys, graphs and statistics (Saunders et al., 2016, p 166). Quantitative studies can sometimes overly simplify by only focusing on the numerical data (Bryman, 2004; Saunders et al., 2016 p 166). This approach fails to identify complexity in using numbers alone and misses out on the relationships and other human factor dynamics (Bryman, 2004). Qualitative methods, on the other hand, are more associated with exploring human experiences and perspectives to develop a theoretical framework (Bryman, 2004; Saunders et al., 2016 p 166).

For this study, the researcher selected a qualitative approach because it focuses on understanding the complicated nuances of how leadership styles influence readiness. The research questions posed during the semi-structured interviews can be found at Appendix 1. In addition to interviews, the study includes document analysis by using the Commanding Officer’s Letter of Direction which can be found at Appendix 2 and the Operations Officer’s Direction which can be found at Appendix 3. Both documents are primary sources of strategic and operational leadership decision making in a live operational scenario. Using this interpretive framework allowed the researcher to understand how leadership actions impacted personnel, equipment and training readiness within an Attack Aviation Regiment.

3.6 Sampling Strategy and Recruitment

A purposive sampling strategy was selected because it aligns with the qualitative nature of this study. Saunders et al., (2016, p 301) state that this strategy focuses on depth and insight, rather than generalisability. Participants across all ranks and trades were targeted, this was to enable the researcher to gather a broad understanding of how leadership impacts operational readiness. This method ensured the inclusion of Commissioned Officers, Warrant Officers, Senior Non-Commissioned Officers and Junior Non-Commissioned Officers from trades that include Pilots, Engineers, Communication Specialists, Groundcrew Specialists and Logisticians. The study captured differences of leadership experiences and considered potential rank bias by combining perceptions from senior and junior ranks across all trades.

Interview participants were recruited from the Regiment by targeting people with the relevant experience for their rank and trade. Participants were sent an email or approached in person where the study was described in detail. Of the fifteen people invited to take part in the research, eleven replied with a positive response, but only nine were interviewed as two participants were unavailable due to operational commitments. It is worth noting that the four individuals that did not respond were senior officers within the Regiment. In addition to the nine interviews that were conducted, two documents were analysed. These documents were selected because they outline the challenges faced when balancing decision making that directly impacts operational readiness. They provide leadership perspectives from an organisational level, rather than an individual level.

3.7 Data Collection Methods

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews with a cross section of Regimental personnel. This approach provided an advantage over other methods, since it allows you to adapt and change direction as a result of new data emerging (Saunders et al., 2016, p 175). The interviews provided rich data on the diverse perspectives of leadership and how it influences operational readiness. Structured interviews can be useful because they offer a higher response rate and the interviewer can clarify questions to avoid confusion (Queirós et al., 2017). However, they are time-consuming to prepare and lack flexibility because the interview cannot be adjusted, even if new interesting topics arise (Queirós et al., 2017). Semi-structured interviews were chosen over structured interviews because they allow for open ended dialogue while maintaining a structured framework as a handrail (Creswell, 2003, p 21; Bryman, 2016, p 10). This flexibility supported the inductive aspect (in line with interpretivism) and enabled theories and concepts to emerge naturally from the interviews (Saunders et al., 2016, p 175).

The interviews provided an understanding of subjective experiences and professional judgement on personnel, equipment and training readiness. Training readiness often involves subjective judgement and is based on the commander's experience (Junor, 2017; Herrera, 2020). There is a vast amount of equipment within an Attack Aviation Regiment and rather than focusing on equipment holdings as secondary data, the author gathered information directly from the subject matter experts responsible for the management and maintenance of the equipment. This study focused on Apache AH-64E helicopters, ground vehicles that include Oshkosh refuelling vehicles, Land Rover communication platforms and heavy lift vehicles.

The interview questions were created by using a combination of Patton 2002 and Saunders et al. (2016, p 407-409) framework for structuring interviews. The questions were designed to ensure a purposeful but relaxed environment with participants, starting with an icebreaker and progressed to in-depth questions. This approach was flexible and ensured that the interviews were systematic but

remained structured in order to capture the nuanced experiences of how leadership impacts operational readiness. As the study also utilises document analysis as primary data, the Commanding Officer’s Letter of Direction serves as high level strategic intent which outlines the priorities in a time constrained and operational context. The Operations Officer’s direction translates the Commanding Officers strategic intent into actionable tasks that captures leadership application at the operational and tactical levels.

3.8 Pilot Study

A pilot interview was conducted which provided valuable feedback and informed the final interview guide. The author altered the initial questions because they lacked focus and were not structured effectively enough to get the information required. The pilot study interviewee found that the questions were unclear and open to interpretation. The author’s inexperience in conducting interviews by using academic language made the questions difficult to understand. To address these issues, adjustments were made to simplify the questions by using normal language.

3.9 Priori Themes

A priori themes were used to focus the analysis on styles of leadership and operational readiness. The themes were selected from the key concepts explored in the literature review and also because of their relevance to the research aim and objectives (King & Brooks 2017). Using a priori themes assisted the researcher with speeding up the coding process (King & Brooks’ 2017). To avoid a blinkered effect, the author followed King & Brooks’ (2017) guidance by deliberately limiting the amount of themes. The selected themes are broken down to leadership styles, which can be found in Table 3 and operational readiness, which can be found in Table 4.

Table 3: Leadership Priori Themes

Priori Themes	Definition
Transformational Leadership	Inspires and motivates people through vision, innovation and personal development.
Transactional Leadership	Relies on a transaction that is based on rewards and discipline to maintain efficiency, structure and compliance.
Servant Leadership	Prioritises the needs of the team to create trust and support.
Laissez-faire Leadership	Provides autonomy with little supervision but relies on a skilled and well-motivated team.

Table 4: Readiness Priori Themes

Priori Themes	Definition
Operational Readiness	“The period measured from an initiation order to the moment when the headquarters or unit is ready to perform its task from its peacetime location (permanent or forward deployed) or ready for deployment.” (JDP 0-01, 2022),
Personnel Readiness	The physical, mental and professional preparedness of personnel to meet operational demands.
Equipment Readiness	The serviceability, availability and maintenance of equipment to support operations.
Training Readiness	The level of collective and individual preparedness through structured training to execute missions.

3.10 Data Analysis

Grounded theory was considered for the analysis but disregarded due to its lack of flexibility (Saunders et al. 2016, p 595). A deductive approach to data analysis was also disregarded, the author’s reason for this was because deduction is typically associated with theory driven research (Saunders et al. 2016, p 51) that is used for interpreting quantitative data (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 71). Instead, the author selected an inductive approach to analyse the data because it is more suitable for analysing qualitative data (O’Gorman & Macintosh, 2015, p 71) and allows for leadership theories to emerge (Bryman, 2004; Saunders et al., 2016). The author used a combination of Bryman’s (2016) Data Reduction Method and King & Brooks’ (2017) Template Analysis to assist with the initial organisation of the data. These approaches were used due to the large volume of data to be analysed (Bryman, 2016); King & Brooks, 2017).

After familiarising with the data, NVivo was used to preliminary code data that the author thought would be useful, an NVivo screenshot of the preliminary codes can be found at Appendix 4. The coded data was then manually extracted from NVivo and clustered into the specific priori themes by using King & Brooks’ (2017) Template Analysis Framework. The process of Bryman’s (2016) Data Reduction Method assisted with the organisation of the large amount of data. Some overlaps of themes were identified during this process which required an iterative approach to refine the categories and ensure the data was placed where it added the most value to produce the initial template. The application and development of the template continued as an iterative process that involved systematically analysing the data to ensure that it was relevant to the research objectives. Differing perspectives were compared as the analysis progressed, this allowed for a nuanced interpretation of the findings. This process continued to ensure the analysis remained robust and coherent and resulted in the final template being produced. Figure 3 demonstrates the steps that were taken to analyse the data.

Figure 3: Typical Steps in Template Analysis (King & Brooks, 2017)

The Commanding Officer's and Operations Officer's directives were also analysed by using King & Brooks' (2017) Template Analysis in the same way as the interviews. Key phrases and orders were highlighted to familiarise with the data before proceeding to preliminary coding through identifying operational constraints, leadership statements and direction. The analysis of the semi-structured interviews and directives were conducted separately. The integration of these data points will be presented in the Findings Chapter and aligned with the research aim and objectives in the Discussion Chapter.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was granted by the University of Staffordshire Ethics Committee. During the research period, there was a change of Commanding Officers. The previous Commanding Officer authorised the Regiment to be used as a case study and the new Commanding Officer authorised its continued use. Bell & Bryman (2007) emphasise the importance of consent, data protection and ethical challenges. For this study, consent was obtained before interviewing and assured all participants that their responses would remain anonymous. Interviews were conducted in private via Microsoft Teams. The Commanding Officer authorised the Letter of Direction and the Operations Officer's Direction to be used as part of the research project. Data protection measures were implemented and the secure storage of all recordings and transcripts were restricted to the researcher only. In terms of ethical challenges, it is important to create an environment that makes participants feel secure and able to speak openly (Bell & Bryman, 2007). This was important when

discussing topics like leadership within an Army unit to encourage honest and open responses. The author reassured participants that the interview was not to assess performance.

3.12 Limitations

Jick (1979) explains that every research method has its limitations and that any single method used possibly cancels out the other. Jick (1979) suggests that various methods should be used to collect data, such as mixing interviews with observations on performance. For example, a leader's effectiveness could be judged by interviewing and observing their behaviour, then reviewing their performance and the outcome of their task. A more reliable understanding of how effective the leader performs is provided if all these methods lead to the same conclusion. This study includes the method of document analysis to compliment the interview data. Using this approach allowed for an element of triangulation to ensure the intent from official communications is compared to the lived experiences and perceptions of lower ranks. Integrating both of these methods enhanced the project's depth and reliability to assess how leadership impacts operational readiness. Due to the small-scale nature of this qualitative study, the research is open to broader limitations. The sample size is relatively modest with nine interviews conducted and two documents analysed. According to Saunders et al. (2016, p 279-280), the sampling size can affect the depth and accuracy of the findings. Managing power dynamics shaped who was interviewed, how the questions were asked and protected anonymity. The researcher mitigated this issue by exploring the lived experiences of junior ranks and gaining their perceptions of how their commanders leadership impacts operational readiness.

Only one senior leader took part in the study. The absence of the wider senior officer cohort may have limited the depth of research from a senior leader perspective. Edgar H. Schein (2010 p. 237-241) notes that leaders ignore what they do not value or they may have an assumption about exposure. The reason for their lack of engagement is not known but could be due to other commitments, time constraints or reluctance to be involved in the research project. The Army has a strict hierarchical structure. The researcher considered that senior ranks might have provided favourable responses due to reputational consequences (Saunders et al., 2016, p 341). Junior ranks may have been hesitant to provide honest views with the fear that their comments could have a negative impact on their career (Saunders et al., 2016, p 342). To mitigate, the researcher ensured anonymity and confidentiality during the interviews to provide a safe environment and assured the participants that this was the case. Saunders et al., (2016, p 194-195) claim that theoretical saturation happens when no new themes or information emerges during data collection. Saturation was harder to achieve while participants were performing time sensitive duties. To mitigate, the researcher deconflicted participants' commitments and allowed flexibility to

accommodate deployment and Regimental responsibilities to ensure the collection of meaningful data.

Conducting and analysing qualitative data from semi-structured interviews is time consuming (Bryman, 2004; Saunders et al., 2016, p 414). The researcher conducted and transcribed the interviews via Microsoft Teams due to Regimental commitments as a means of mitigating this issue. The quality of the data is important for maintaining the credibility of qualitative research, particularly when addressing potential biases (Saunders et al., 2016, p 203). Interview bias happens when a researcher interprets the data with their own bias and allows their own views to influence responses (Saunders et al., 2016, p 397). Interviewee bias is when participants adjust their responses to provide desirable answers (Saunders et al., 2016, p 719). This is particularly relevant within this study because the Army monitors and reports on performance and conduct. The author ensured credibility by maintaining a neutral stance when interpreting the data. The nature of the study was explained, and confidentiality was assured in order to build trust and encourage honest responses. To provide a balanced perspective, a diverse range of ranks and trades were selected to participate and to ensure representation from across the Regiment.

3.13 Summary

This chapter justified the author's selection of the qualitative research approach to examine how leadership impacts operational readiness within an Attack Aviation Regiment. An interpretivist framework helped to guide the research and focus on participant perspectives. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and document analysis was used as a second primary source. The analysis combined data reduction methods and utilised template analysis to examine the data. Ethical considerations that protect individuals and operational deployments were addressed and limitations that mention sample size and the unit preparing for an imminent deployment are also discussed. With the methodology and analysis framework now established, the next chapter will present the findings from the research.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the research data by explaining and evidencing how leadership impacts readiness within the Regiment. As established in the previous chapter, the findings were identified by adopting a qualitative approach and conducting semi-structured interviews, template analysis and document analysis. The findings will be presented in line with the research objectives and across four top-level themes that include: leadership impact, personnel readiness, equipment readiness and training readiness. This chapter will conclude with a summary of the key findings.

4.2 Leadership Impact

This section presents the findings on how leadership impacted operational readiness within the Regiment. The evidence was taken from the Commanding Officer's Directive, the Operations Officer's direction and the information provided by interview participants. Four main leadership styles emerged throughout: transformational, transactional, servant and laissez-faire leadership. Each of these styles shaped how the Regiment's priorities were communicated, resourced and executed.

The Commanding Officer's directive provided clear intent and priorities of work. As the Commanding Officer explains:

My priorities until deployment are:

- 1. DELIVER aircrew competency.*
- 2. PREPARE for (Redacted).*
- 3. SUSTAIN and, where not in contradiction to Priority 1, ENHANCE readiness.*

Common to all is the requirement to PROTECT our workforce.

The emphasis on protecting the workforce was reiterated:

Our people are our vital ground; we must endeavour to protect our workforce and maintain morale to sustain our capability over the longer term. (Commanding Officer)

The Operations Officer provided direction and support to planning:

We will be going back to a Regimental Flypro Coord every Thursday at 1500 to plan out the flying for the following week.

A performance driven approach to meet flying targets was taken:

Weekend flying will be a thing. If we start to fall behind on the 75 hours we need to fly a week we will fly on Saturdays. (Operations Officer)

The directive is not just about giving orders, the Commanding Officer asks commanders at all levels to explain the why:

I need you to ensure that our people understand the reasons for this approach. Please take the time to explain why they may need to refocus activity. (Commanding Officer)

This approach was confirmed during an interview with Participant 7 who described servant leadership as:

Looking after your people and giving them the resources that they need, giving them the direction that they need.

Participant 1 described the risks associated with laissez-faire leadership by explaining:

You encourage creativity, but they lack direction. You can't just say, here's a task, crack on, I'll see you later.

4.3 Personnel Readiness

This section will present the findings on how leadership influences personal readiness. Leaders at all levels have a direct responsibility for developing their subordinates and ensuring they are physically fit, mentally robust and professionally competent. Strong leadership sets the conditions to maintain readiness. Leading by example through their own actions builds credibility and trust. As Participant 1 states:

Value-based leadership, leading by example, setting the standard and being a role model.

Understanding each soldier's strengths and weaknesses is important when developing people to meet the Regiment's operational demands. Effective leadership relies upon knowing your soldiers. This knowledge allows the leader to tailor their development approach to ensure people are physically fit, mentally prepared and professionally competent. As Participant 5 mentioned:

So, knowing that person and understanding how to get the most out of them.

Leaders are responsible for the physical and mental resilience of their teams which can be built up by challenging them in controlled and challenging conditions.

Challenging people, putting them in adverse situations where they have to grow and rise to the challenge, giving them opportunities to be fit and eat good food, it's all part of good mental preparedness. (Participant 4)

The findings from the interviews suggests that communication is generally poor within the Regiment. When discussing deployments, Participant 7 stated:

Communication works both ways up and down. There's a lack of communication and a lack of guidance from higher.

Managing the tempo of operations and commitments is an important leadership function. This is particularly crucial within the Regiment because the tempo can be challenging but also motivating.

The tempo's quite high at the minute, but for the young guys, they want that. I think they like to get out the door. It's like being a lifeguard and never getting in the water. (Participant 7)

This highlights how keen the young soldiers are to deploy. However, Participant 5 highlighted how the tempo can create additional pressure by saying:

At the moment it's very busy, very, very busy. I think we're only going to get busier, talking about working weekends, so it's a lot of pressure on individuals. (Participant 5)

4.4 Equipment Readiness

Maintaining equipment readiness in the Regiment is challenging and relies heavily upon effective leadership at all levels. The interviews revealed a clear distinction between how leadership focus is different with aircraft, vehicles and other essential ground support equipment. There are additional pressures placed on Regimental leadership by the wider military aviation environment. Participant 1 explained his viewpoint as:

Aviation is such a high-pressure, high-performance environment, our goals are often split or constantly changing, so it kind of stretches the leadership team.

This leadership challenge is compounded by the need to maintain safety standards, as Participant 1 continued to state:

In army aviation, safety is always our key factor, but it's just an added constraint, sometimes leadership I think can drop down the pecking order for some people because they feel they've got a mission to achieve or an output to achieve.

Leaders within the Regiment demonstrate a very strong commitment to the serviceability of the aircraft fleet. Participant 2 puts it into context:

If the aircraft fleet went down because of serviceability, it would be a massive thing, right? So, the leadership tree is hugely bought into that space, and they will bend over backwards to make changes.

Maintaining aircraft readiness is an operational necessity. Participant 5 notes:

We're always on top of serviceability for aircraft. If we don't have aircraft, there's no point in going out the door.

Participant 5 continues to discuss equipment:

If we break this equipment, it'd be dangerous and incur cost as well. So I'd be more authoritarian towards equipment care and readiness because this stuff will save lives.

A noticeable gap appeared when it came to discussing mission critical equipment other than aircraft. The interviews of Regimental personnel revealed additional leadership challenges.

Aviation tends to get a lot of attention and a lot of resources and a lot of thought, whereas the land side of things, until it becomes an issue and affects the aviation side, it's kind of not in the forefront of people's minds. (Participant 8)

This was backed by Participant 2 when discussing how the prioritisation of GSE does not match the emphasis placed on aircraft:

When it comes to other equipment such as vehicles or GSE, you don't get as much buy in.

This confirms that unless equipment such as Oshkosh Refuelling Vehicles which directly affect flying sorties, leadership attention can drift elsewhere. Managing the Regiment's large vehicle fleet

presents leaders with difficult challenges. With over 200 ageing platforms that are prone to faults, managing and maintaining them at readiness standards needs a sustained leadership effort.

Participant 3 remarked:

The amount of green fleet we have that's unserviceable and struggles to get going is ridiculous. It seems to break down every two minutes.

This challenge is highlighted further and intensified by workforce constraints, where at one point, Participant 4 highlighted:

They had over 200 platforms and only eight people who could turn a spanner.

4.5 Training Readiness

The Regiment is held at high readiness and is prepared to conduct operations across the full spectrum of conflict. Strong leadership plays a really important role in maintaining this state of readiness to ensure all personnel within the Regiment are trained to the highest standard.

Participant 5 explained:

We're held at readiness, what we're doing is warfighting and it's not counter insurgency operations anymore, it's peer on peer. Now we're training for that, working more tactically in a space they're normally uncomfortable with.

A constant challenge within the Regiment is balancing the training priorities between aircrew and groundcrew. Aircrew training often takes precedence and is driven by the focus to maintain flying hours, while groundcrew training is frequently the first thing to be sacrificed.

I think that sometimes aircrew mission sets get prioritised over groundcrew. The groundcrew training basically falls to Squadrons. (Participant 5)

Effective training happens within the Regiment, especially when aircrew and groundcrew integrate and operate together. Participant 5 emphasised the point:

We try to work with the aircrew as much as possible, get them flying into Forward Arming Refuelling Points so they know what our actions are going to be and they know what we're going to do.

Leaders within the unit also drive realistic and threat-based scenarios that reflect current warfare such as the use of drones. Participant 2 described a serial from a recent exercise:

They arranged actual scenarios where drones were up and people were having to check before leaving their hides and harbours or before occupying their locations.

Interviewees agreed that there is no single style of leadership that suits the delivery of training. Participant 4 stated:

It's a mixture of all styles depending on what's needed.

Participant 7 stated that:

Good instructors don't just tell people what to do, they help them understand how to do it and why to do it. Take weapon sights as an example, if you teach them how to adjust them and why, they then understand the process, they're learning.

Leaders within the Regiment balance risk by making effective decisions. Participant 2 summarised it by saying:

Leaders prioritise where the risk is held, they need to decide if the risk is held with equipment, personnel, or training readiness.

This statement is backed by the Commanding Officer's direction that identifies the low levels of experienced aircrew as a risk to operational effectiveness. Participant 5 continues to describe risks:

Risks need to be taken, we're in the Army. We land helicopters in fields and put bombs on them, but we could be doing it under fire or having drones diving in on us, that is risky. So, if we can't train to a standard that makes us good, when it happens for real, we're going to come off worse because we haven't been able to practice realistically.

Some interview participants defined training readiness as the quality of training that has been undertaken, while other define it as hours flown.

Some people will measure that realistic and robust training means we are operationally ready. Some people will measure that aircraft hours flown means we are operationally ready.
(Participant 4)

This statement highlights the difference in perspectives that Regimental leaders take into consideration when deciding to hold risk against training readiness.

4.6 Summary

The findings demonstrate that leadership plays a really important role in shaping the Regiment's operational readiness. The evidence suggests that issuing clear direction with the Regiment's priorities influences how it prepares for deployments. Personnel readiness and resilience is established, maintained and developed through supportive leadership that challenges the soldiers. Aircraft serviceability and aircrew training are often the priority, but collaborative and realistic training enhances readiness across all departments. The tempo of operations and communication appear to have mixed opinions. The next chapter will discuss these findings and relate them to the existing literature.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The aim of this study was to examine the impact leadership has on operational readiness by analysing how different leadership styles affect personnel, equipment and training readiness. This chapter combines the existing literature with the findings from this study to identify gaps within the current research. The author introduces the concept of “leadership driven readiness” which is based on the analysis and suggests that leadership behaviours and actions play a critical role in enhancing and maintaining individual and collective readiness. Further discussion on the implications of the concept will be highlighted and how it contributes to the understanding of how leadership impacts operational readiness.

5.2 Leadership Impact

It is clear to see that leadership plays an important role in establishing and maintaining operation readiness. The Commanding Officer’s Direction is a strong example of transformational leadership through transparent communication that created a unified vision. This aligns with aspects of Avolio et al., (1991) Four I’s by articulating a compelling vision through inspirational motivation to achieve success. Intellectual stimulation was also present by challenging people to think and innovate (Avolio et al., 1991) by being “*agile in the approach*” to achieving personal readiness. The direction also encourages supporting and developing readiness through individualised consideration by protecting and the workforce, the Commanding Officer’s “*vital ground*”. This approach is supported by Sinek’s (2011) concept of inspiring subordinates to connect their efforts to the vision.

The Commanding Officer identifies that there is a low level of aircrew experience which is a risk to mission success. This concern is supported by Herrera (2020) who argues that training readiness is difficult to measure and relies on the commanders’ judgement. In response, the Commanding Officer prioritised aircrew competency to ensure they are at the standard expected to be able to carry out missions. This involves building initial readiness, increasing readiness and maintaining readiness in line with Herrera’s (2020) three key stages of readiness. If the aircrew are not competent, no level of equipment readiness or other form of deployment preparation will ensure success. These principles align with Army’s strategic goals of preparedness as defined in JDP 0-01 (2022) and a visual representation is illustrated in the Literature Review at Figure 2 (Herrera, 2020).

The Commanding Officer’s Directive displays clear evidence of servant leadership. He explicitly states that the people are the vital ground and recognises that morale is important for operational

success. By explaining why activities have been refocused builds trust and shows respect to the soldiers doing the work. This approach reflects on Greenleaf's (2008) views that effective leaders guide others with clarity and purpose. It also aligns with Sinek's (2011) "why" philosophy which creates a culture that is built on purpose and shared success.

The Operations Officer's formal direction displayed transactional leadership by setting expectation, providing clear tasks and holding people accountable. The direction is task focused and backed by consequences if the targets were not met. This style of leadership strongly resembles Burns' (1978) definition of transactional leadership as an exchange. In this case, the interaction between leader and follower is the shared understanding of the direction issued from the Operations Officer down the chain of command, this aligns with Tavanti's (2008) theory that transactional leadership is suitable within the military because it focuses on structure and the adherence to rules.

The academic literature often states that transactional leadership lacks a common purpose or shared goal (Burns, 1978; Avolio and Bass, 2001; Bass et al., 2003). However, the Operations Officer's direction arguably blends transactional leadership in the form of control, to create a common purpose and shared goal of achieving flying competence. Although the means of achieving the main effort are transactional, the collective goal served as a readiness aim. This suggests that a more nuanced style of leadership should be applied than what the theory suggests. Avolio and Bass (2001) and Bass et al., (2003) mention that innovation and creativity is limited with transactional leadership because the focus is primarily on compliance. It could be argued that this situation encourages innovation through agility in problem solving and adapting training to meet the standards. As Ulmer (2010) states, the core purpose of any Army's leadership is to get the job done.

There was a deliberate avoidance of laissez-faire leadership within the directives from Regimental Headquarters. The Regiment was under pressure and tasks needed to be coordinated to maximise flying hours in order to deliver operational output. One of the risks associated with laissez-faire leadership is that it can "*encourage creativity, but it lacks direction*" (Participant 1). This is confirmed by Mokhtar and Yunus (2023) who raised concerns about the lack of direction which leads to confusion and a lack of productivity. Wang et al., (2023) also highlight how this style is regularly associated with delayed decision making and ignoring problems.

These examples support the researchers emerging concept of leadership driven readiness where the leader's actions and style, even though they contradict the theory, can still produce results that positively influences the readiness outcome. In this scenario, transactional methods were used to drive a measurable progress by sharing the vision and a common goal. The next section will focus on the influence leadership has on personnel readiness.

5.3 Personnel Readiness

The findings suggest that strong leadership sets the conditions to maintain readiness. By knowing their people, leaders within the Regiment adapted their approach towards developing their subordinates to ensure they were prepared for the operational environment they are deploying to. The evidence from the findings demonstrates that leaders are applying the Army Leadership Code by knowing and understanding their people, or “*recognising individual strengths and weaknesses*” as the Director Leadership (2021) states. Leaders have demonstrated an understanding of their people’s individual needs and adjusted their development accordingly, this approach also “*encourages confidence in the team,*” which is another principle of the Army Leadership Code (Director Leadership, 2021). Leaders within the Regiment display the highest standards of service behaviours and encourage their subordinates to follow. This reflects on the “*lead by example*” principle from the Army Leadership Code (Director Leadership, 2021), which demonstrates high standards of discipline that encourages their soldiers to act in the same way and meet the same expectations, aligning with the “*demand high performance*” principle (Director Leadership, 2021). By using the Army Leadership Code as an approach, it reinforces accountability and strengthens the team and individual readiness to meet the Regiment’s operational demands. This highlights the importance of personal knowledge so that leaders can provide the right opportunities for growth by investing time in and understanding their people.

Communication emerged as an unexpected theme. Although there is no specific literature related directly to communication in the Literature Review, it could be argued that effective communication is a critical function of command that has a direct impact on personnel readiness. Shmelova et al., (2023) mention that collaboration and communication promote aviation safety. Clear and timely communication allows soldiers to plan and prepare accordingly. Poor communication leads to confusion and has a negative impact on personnel readiness because soldiers do not understand what they are doing or why they are doing it. Although there is an apparent contradiction with communication, as the directives from the Commanding Officer and Operations Officer were examples of effective communication. This could be perceived as a one-off situation due to the specific focus on aircrew competency and flying output, suggesting that the perceptions in this situation are not applied across all other areas of the Regiment.

There is clear evidence that leaders are managing the balance between motivation and preventing burnout. Due to the high-performance nature of the Regiment, maintaining a high operational tempo is critical to the success in achieving readiness and leaders are balancing tempo with recovery in order to achieve success. This challenge relates with Adair’s (2009) Action Centred Leadership where individual development, team cohesion and achieving the task must be

balanced to ensure operational effectiveness is maintained. The importance of managing this challenge is confirmed by Pendleton (2019) who reported that high tempos within Combat Aviation Brigades has a negative effect on morale and overall readiness.

The concept of leadership driven readiness is now incorporating behaviours from the Army Leadership Code. Effective communication is also included to enable direction, prevent confusion and ensure readiness is achieved, because without communication, the leader will not be able to apply the Army Leadership Code. Managing the tempo is another aspect of how decision making can directly support readiness and sustainability which echoes Adair's (2009) model of balancing development, task and cohesion. The next discussion point will focus on how equipment readiness is maintained through effective leadership.

5.4 Equipment Readiness

Leaders within the Regiment are balancing safety, delivering output and maintaining equipment readiness. Navigating the pressures of a high-performance Attack Aviation Regiment is a difficult challenge. Leaders within the Regiment and higher up the chain of command are proactive and willing to make difficult decisions to ensure aircraft safety and readiness is maintained. This reflects the research conducted by Osman et al., (2021) who state that leadership is the most influential factor for maintaining safety and operational effectiveness in the aviation industry. This statement on the relationship between leadership and aviation safety is confirmed by Haddon-Cave (2009), Ayiei et al., (2020) and Bastola (2020).

There appears to be a general agreement that the aircraft serviceability is prioritised, and attention only turns to land systems when problems that impact flying happen. This suggests that vehicle and other equipment maintenance is not managed with the same foresight and a more reactive approach is taken for this equipment. Participant 5 mentions: *"If we don't have aircraft, there's no point in going out the door."* This creates a paradox and appears to be a logical thought process, but the critical reality is overlooked, because if the aircraft support equipment is not serviceable, the aircraft will be ineffective when deployed. As Herrera (2020) states, maintaining equipment readiness includes the continuous equipping of the unit to enable operations. If vehicles and ground support equipment serviceability is not managed with the same foresight, the equipment operators will not have confidence in the equipment and it will have a negative impact on fighting spirit (JDP 0-01, 2022). This confirms the challenges that leaders must face when balancing operational output against longer term sustainment.

Leaders within the Regiment must maintain mission critical equipment to a high standard in order to meet readiness standards. Leaders that are responsible for maintaining the equipment will often

adopt a more direct and authoritarian approach to ensure it remains serviceable to enable operations (Herrera, 2020). This authoritarian style of leadership signifies the high-risk consequences of equipment failure and the potential impact to operations. Some departments within the Regiment are lacking in workforce and work under pressure to meet readiness standards, sometimes with the work ethic to exceed what the chain of command expects from them. This caused another leadership challenge, to balance the “*demand of high performance*” (Director Leadership, 2021) against the need to manage morale and the tempo (Pendleton, 2019).

Leadership driven readiness involves balancing safety with competing priorities and workforce constraints. Especially within high performance environments like Army aviation, leaders must prioritise mission critical equipment without neglecting other platforms. Leaders must maintain high standards and manage effectively with limited resources without causing burnout. Leadership driven readiness is not just about giving clear direction but about creating a safe working environment that can be sustained to deliver operational readiness across all platforms. The next section will look at the relationship between leadership and training readiness.

5.5 Training Readiness

Leaders of all ranks ensure that realistic and relevant training is delivered to Regimental personnel to enable and sustain operational readiness commitments. As stated by Herrera (2020), units held at readiness can increase readiness through a combination of training and preparing for rapid deployments. Aircrew and groundcrew maintain high levels of warfighting proficiency and operate in tactical environments outside of their comfort zones in order to build resilience and make people comfortable with being uncomfortable. Building resilience in rapidly changing environments aligns with the modern readiness strategy quoted by Børge Brende (2022). The more experienced commanders within the Regiment are mentoring their soldiers as they adapt to these challenging training serials. Collective training that includes aircrew and groundcrew improves teamwork and increases situational awareness through the understanding of each other’s roles (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). Participant 5 states: “*they know what our actions are going to be and they know what we’re going to do.*” This is supported by Shmelova et al., (2023) who mention that collaborative training in the aviation industry increases safety and communication.

There is a perception that senior leaders within the Regimental do not fully buy in to supporting ground training. This leaves junior commanders to fend for themselves to deliver training with limited resources and support. However, this perception is not a negative point, it may not mean a lack of engagement from senior leaders. The principles of mission command emphasise trust, empowerment and decentralised decision making (Greenleaf, 2002; JDP 0-01, 2022). Operating within the commander’s intent allows the junior leaders to innovate and develop their own

challenging training (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007; Konradt, 2014). Both of these perspectives raise another paradox. The positive side is that mission command empowers junior leaders by encouraging innovation and decision making (Director Leadership, 2021; Jamon J., 2023). The negative side is that mission command could lead to inconsistent training standards and uneven readiness across the Squadrons (Jamon J., 2023). This demonstrates how important it is for senior leaders to balance control with autonomy to sustain training readiness. The perception of limited support may be caused by the nature of mission command, because the findings appear to suggest that senior leaders are enabling the ground training through empowerment.

More generally, training within the Regiment is delivered in a structured manner and through visionary leadership that adapts training to meet the changing characteristics of war. The war in Ukraine is a more recent example that highlights how training must be continuously adapted to meet the demands of the contemporary operating environment (Crombe and Nagl, 2023). Leaders within the Regiment actively designed realistic training that resembles the contemporary environment by incorporating counterintelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance training serials through the use of drones. Herrera (2020) states that training readiness is difficult to measure and often relies upon the commander's judgement. Perceptions of training readiness within the Regiment vary, some think that realistic and arduous training sets the benchmark, while others may focus on aircraft hours flown or aircrew competency.

Leadership driven readiness reflects upon how leaders design, deliver and adapt training to make it realistic and meet the characteristics of the operating environment they are deploying to. Leaders must employ the mission command framework and provide strategic vision to empower and develop subordinates, they must balance control and autonomy while providing tactical level support. It is not just about having training in place, it is about "*encouraging thinking*" at the junior levels, "*encouraging confidence in the team*" and "*demanding high performance*" (Director Leadership, 2021) to develop the right mindset for operational deployments.

5.6 Summary

This chapter has demonstrated that operational readiness can be enhanced by leaders that think and act with agility. Regimental leaders connect their teams by sharing a vision and mission success relies upon protecting the workforce, knowing the people and effective communication. Contrary to the academic literature, there is evidence that shows transactional leadership can be combined with a clear vision that drives focus and readiness. Empowerment through mission command, realistic training and the prioritisation and management of risk emerged as key themes. Leaders within the Regiment are balancing many competing demands, but as stated by Ulmer

(2010), the purpose of an Army leader is to get the job done. These points set the stage for the Conclusion Chapter where the research aim and objectives are revisited.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

This chapter will provide the key findings of the research and connect them to the aim and objectives. It will also demonstrate how it contributes to theoretical and practical knowledge. A reminder of the methodological limitations is provided and practical recommendations on how leadership practices can enhance operational readiness are offered. The author provides suggestions for future academic research that may increase the understanding of how leadership practices impact operational readiness.

6.2 Research Aim and Objectives

As a reminder, this research project examined the impact leadership has on operational readiness by analysing how different leadership styles affect personnel, equipment and training readiness. The following research objectives were established:

6.2.1 Research Objective 1: Examine the impact of leadership styles on operational readiness

Leadership style has a significant impact on operational readiness because it influences how units perform and adapt to maintain readiness standards. Leadership style is more than providing direction and control, it is the driver of operational readiness that influences how the teams perform and adapt to maintain the standards. Applying transactional leadership with a clear vision proved to be an effective way of driving performance and striving to achieve, maintain and increase readiness. Mission command principles enhanced agility and empowered subordinate leaders to achieve readiness standards within the commander's intent. Commanders that communicated effectively and understood how to get the best out of their people, maintained readiness across all areas.

6.2.2 Research Objective 2: Assess the influence of leadership on personnel readiness

Transformational and servant leadership styles were more effective at influencing personnel readiness in a positive way. Leadership styles that enable trust and support, encourage confidence and commitment to achieve, maintain and develop personal readiness standards. Leading by example to set the standards inspired and motivated subordinates. Transformational leaders inspired their people through vision, challenging their subordinates in a safe environment and

supporting their development. Leaders that prioritised morale and the needs of their team through servant leadership created a supportive environment that made them feel valued.

6.2.3 Research Objective 3: Evaluate the role leadership plays in maintaining equipment readiness

Leadership played a critical role in maintaining equipment readiness, leaders set the standards and ensured safety was prioritised. Having confidence in the equipment enhances morale and fighting spirit (JDP 0-01, 2022), this is especially important in Army aviation. Within this high risk and high-performance Regiment, leaders prioritised aircraft over ground support equipment because aircraft faults can result in a risk to life. Leaders within the Regiment faced a difficult challenge to balance priorities across all platforms to enable ground vehicles to effectively support the aircraft. Without the ground vehicles, the aircraft would be ineffective. Leaders had to manage workforce constraints and operational tempos to ensure safety standards were maintained and readiness standards were achieved.

6.2.4 Research Objective 4: Examine the relationship between leadership and training readiness

Leaders played a key role in shaping training readiness. There appeared to be a divide between strong leadership at the junior level and a perception that senior leaders do not provide as much support to ground training. Effective and realistic training increased resilience but required oversight and support from senior leaders. It is evident that senior leaders apply mission command and empower junior leaders to design and deliver effective and realistic training. It is not known how the training standards across the Squadrons differ due to this autonomy, but it does highlight that all commanders balance control with freedom of action to ensure realistic training is delivered.

6.3 Contribution to Theory and Practice

This research project introduced the concept of leadership driven readiness which builds upon and adapts the Army Leadership Code and other academic leadership theories. In true Army style, where no concept is complete without an acronym, the researcher presents a model that supports leadership driven readiness. "VOICES": Vision, Ownership, Initiative, Communication, Equilibrium and Standards.

Vision. Provides a shared purpose that aligns everyone with the mission. A clear vision inspires collective effort and helps every member of the team understand their role. Leaders must

reinforce their vision through regular briefings to ensure that everyone understands their purpose to support readiness.

Ownership. Facilitates empowerment through the principles of mission command. This decentralises authority and promotes accountability within the commander's intent. In turn, this allows leaders at all levels to build confidence and promote innovation to achieve readiness standards.

Initiative. Agile thinking and proactive decision making are critical in unpredictable high tempo environments. Plans can change often in dynamic environments, waiting for direction can delay action and compromise readiness. Solving problems and reacting early will enhance operational effectiveness.

Communication. Effective communication enables the team to put the plan into action. Effective communication reduces ambiguity and allows every member of the team to understand their part in the plan. Communication can be delivered in different forms such as face to face or by email, but it must be concise and effective, especially when working as decentralised teams.

Equilibrium. Balancing control, operational tempo, safety and morale promotes sustainability. Leaders must balance these aspects of competing demands without compromising on standards. Sustaining operational readiness in high performance environments is achieved by adjusting workloads and prioritising tasks that do not compromise on safety.

Standards. Professional conduct and discipline set the example that encourages others to do the same. Doing the right thing all of the time promotes cohesion and inspires better performance. Effective leadership through role modelling the highest standards of behaviour increases operational readiness.

The concept of leadership driven readiness provides a practical framework that can be used at any level of leadership to adapt to dynamic situations and empower their teams to establish, maintain or develop operational readiness.

6.4 Limitations

As a reminder, this research project was conducted using qualitative methods. The sampling size was small with nine semi-structured interviews conducted, due to the modest sampling size, the depth and accuracy could be affected (Saunders et al. 2016, p 279-280). Two documents were

analysed to offer a form of triangulation (Jick, 1979) against formal leadership intent and the lived experiences of people within the Regiment. The absence of senior officer engagement may also limit the depth of experiences at the senior leadership level of the Regiment. Although one senior officer participated, it does not capture the wider operational and strategic views, this must be considered if other units try to replicate the findings. Bias affects reliability (Saunders et al., 2016, p 719) and the researcher acknowledged that senior ranks might have provided favourable responses to protect their reputation (Saunders et al., 2016, p 341). Junior ranks might have been reluctant to provide honest opinions with the fear that their comments could have a negative impact on their career (Saunders et al., 2016, p 342). This study is unique because it focuses on a high-performance, high-risk Attack Aviation Regiment and explores leadership in a live operational context. Creswell (2007, p 74) states that a case study presents an “*unusual or unique situation.*” Combining this specific case with these limitations confirms that reliability and replicability are naturally restricted. The next section will cover the final research objective and provide recommendations for future research.

6.5 Research Objective 5: Provide recommendations on how leadership practices enhance operational readiness

The researcher recommends that the practical application of the leadership driven readiness principles (vision, ownership, initiative, communication, equilibrium and standards) will continue to shape the culture of the Regiment and enhance team performance, which in turn, will sustain operational readiness. Commanders at all levels must consistently communicate a clear and compelling vision. This will create focus and motivation which will enhance operational readiness. The vision must be translated into action and leaders will need to create the conditions that allows subordinates to take ownership of their responsibilities. Decentralised decision-making will empower leaders at all levels and build confidence as well as responsiveness, this principle of mission command will ensure readiness is sustained without continuous supervision. Ownership must be backed with encouragement to act decisively and with initiative, this is especially true in rapidly changing environments such as Army aviation. The use of effective communication will ensure everyone understands their role and will enable commanders at all levels to manage the demands that are placed on their teams. Maintaining the equilibrium between readiness demands and the welfare of personnel is important and will allow personnel to perform with consistency and without burnout. Managing and prioritising tasks without compromising on safety will sustain readiness in the long run. To reinforce all of these actions, leaders must consistently role model the highest standards of behaviour. Operational readiness relies on trust, discipline and professionalism. Leaders that do the right thing and demonstrate all of these behaviours will be able to establish, maintain and develop operational readiness. To enhance the knowledge of how

leadership impacts operational readiness, the author has identified the following areas for future research:

6.6.1 Recommendation for Future Research 1: Quantitative Research to Predict Readiness

During the early stages of the study, the author reviewed literature that focused on the Markov Chain Process which demonstrated how mathematical models can evaluate readiness and reliability. In particular, a study by Żurek et al. (2018) calculated the probability of the readiness of Mi-8 helicopters by using the process. In a separate study of Polish aviation refuelling vehicles by Ziółkowski et al. (2024) used the same process to demonstrate how the mathematical models can predict equipment availability. Quantitative research may compliment this study by providing a different aspect that focuses on numerical data.

6.6.2 Recommendation for Future Research 2: Communication

Communication emerged as an unexpected theme and a potential area to cover a gap through further research. Some participants referred to poor communication, but documented evidence suggested written communication was present. There is a possibility that this messaging could have been diluted as it filtering down the chain of command. It is also possible that the message may not have been passed down at all. This highlights a potential gap in the decentralised structure that could benefit from further research that focuses on leadership communication within decentralised teams.

6.6.3 Recommendation for Future Research 3: Training Standards Across Squadrons

A study that compares how training readiness standards vary between Squadrons may identify how mission command principles contribute to training. Exploring how different leaders understand and apply mission command would determine if autonomy led to an inconsistency of training readiness between Squadrons.

6.6.4 Recommendation for Future Research 4: Inclusion of Senior Leaders

All of the recommendations for future research would benefit from the involvement of senior officers. As the people that are responsible for setting the standards and leading by example, the operational and strategic views these influential people can offer would provide a complete view of how leadership impacts operational readiness.

6.7 Summary

This chapter has presented the key findings and how they relate to the research's aim and objectives. The author has provided theoretical and practical contributions to knowledge on how leadership can positively impact operational readiness. The limitations of the methodology were acknowledged and recommendations of how to increase operational readiness through leadership practices was provided. Areas for future research have been suggested that will build upon this study's findings. The next chapter will focus on the researcher's personal journey throughout the Master of Business Administration (MBA) process.

Chapter 7: Reflection on Learning

7.1 Introduction

Reflective learning is important for continued personal and professional improvement. This chapter uses Kolb's Learning Cycle as the model to reflect on the research process and the author's development throughout the MBA. The MBA competencies are addressed and connected to the author's lived experiences during a demanding time as the unit prepared for and deployed to Eastern Europe. Using first person terms will allow for a more authentic experience on the researcher's reflections and how theories were applied in real time. This chapter will conclude with a summary of the key learning points and explain how they have shaped the author's development.

7.2 Kolb's Learning Cycle

According to Kolb (1984, p 38), learning is: "*The process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience.*" Using Kolb's Learning Cycle as a model for reflection, I will focus on 4 distinct areas: concrete experience, abstract conceptualisation, reflective observation and active experimentation (Kolb & Kolb, 2013).

Throughout the MBA, I have gained concrete experience in applying leadership and management frameworks within a live operational scenario. As my unit prepared for and deployed to Eastern Europe, I have gained valuable experience in applying leadership theories to increase the operational readiness of the unit, helping to ensure a successful deployment. During the pre-deployment phase, I observed how various theories played out in practice. Reflecting on this, two things that really stood out was how different leadership styles affect the culture of the unit and how critical communication is in achieving the goal. I witnessed good and bad points from both which demonstrated how leadership impacted readiness. As I applied abstract concepts to the deployment, I questioned if different leadership styles would have had a different outcome. Doing this helped me connect the theory to the practice. When applying my new knowledge and experimenting with different concepts, I realised that not everyone likes to be asked questions such as "why are we doing this", or "why are we doing it this way." I feel that this is partly because they feel challenged, or they do not have the answers. I now understand that my strengths may expose other people's weaknesses and questions should be framed in a different way to prevent friction. This process has helped me elevate my thinking to a more strategic level. I will now move on to explain how I have achieved the MBA competencies.

7.3 Strategic Agility

This study has been heavily focused around strategic agility. The Ministry of Defence (MOD) sets strategic direction which is shaped by geopolitical relationships. The North Atlantic Treaty Organisation's (NATO) Strategic Concept 2022 states that the Euro-Atlantic area is no longer at peace because of Russia's actions in Ukraine (JDP 0-01, 2022). This means that the MOD must provide strategic direction to maintain readiness in order to react to an adversary. The Ministry of Defence (2015) frames readiness strategies around the questions of: *“ready for what, ready for when and what needs to be ready.”* These questions demonstrate the reality of strategic agility and that Army units need to anticipate a range of threats. I have learnt that strategic agility is more than planning, it is about trying to make sense of uncertainty, making assumptions with limited information and making decisions. When reflecting on my experiences writing this dissertation, especially while reviewing the literature, I felt that providing a vision is extremely important in achieving success. I had never really thought about it with any deep meaning before, but in the Army, commanders deliver orders for operations that always include the commander's “1 up” (the commander's immediate superior) intent and the “2 up” (the superior's immediate superior) intent. I now see this as a practical example of strategic agility being delivered through vision.

7.4 Organisational Agility

Keeping with the theme of the orders process, I recognise that this is a strong example of organisational agility. The orders are formally cascaded down the chain of command until they reach the lowest level, with mission command (freedom for subordinates to act within the commander's intent (JDP 0-01, 2022)) being applied throughout the process. I have learnt from the literature that either stating the “why” or asking the “why” creates a strong organisational culture that provides clarity of purpose (Sinek's, 2011). This sense of purpose results in organisational agility which leads to success. My research project was focused on leadership, which is key to organisational agility and culture. If I were to start again, I would have focussed more on how junior leaders interpret and act on their commander's intent. This may have offered a better understanding into whether the intent gets diluted or misinterpreted as it filters down the chain of command, as this could have a direct impact on operational readiness and organisational agility.

7.5 Customer Focus

It could be argued that the enemy are the Army's customers, because they are the ones that shape what the Army does. However, for the purpose of reflection, I will focus on the Army's internal customers which I class as the soldiers and officers within the chain of command. Although this is not something new that I have learnt during my research, it is clear that people want to be treated with respect. I have observed many times when a soldier has been told what to do in a firm and

direct manner, this is a practice that is more common during operations or field deployments but also happens during routine duties within barracks. While no crime or misconduct has taken place, the delivery of orders can sometimes leave people feeling degraded or humiliated. Part of the hierarchal nature of the Army is obedience to rank and authority, although the command is not disrespectful, subordinates can sometimes perceive the command as disrespectful if it is delivered in the wrong way. This perception can have a negative impact on the leader and follower relationship. This led me down a bit of a rabbit hole to compare the Army's mission first culture with Southwest Airlines' philosophy of "*employees come first and customers come second*," because "*we as leaders must treat our employees as we want them to treat our customers*." (McGee-Cooper et al., 2001). I reflected on these different philosophies to see if there was a way to merge them into a new approach. This idea became more thought provoking when I introduced the enemy as the Army's customer.

7.6 Drive for Results

I have learnt that reactive decision making can achieve short-term results, but they are often at the expense of long-term sustainability. Operational readiness is not a one-off task, it is a continuous demand (Herrera, 2020) that requires long term vision and effective leadership. Ulmer (2010) highlights how military leaders are focused on measurable outputs which explains why the Army excels at producing short term managers. Transactional leadership can support these short-term results and is especially useful in crisis situations (Bass, 1990). Sinek (2011, p. 41) warns us about chasing short-term results as they can harm the long-term health of the organisation. The Army's culture is very focused on results and simply just getting the job done (Ulmer, 2010). When reflecting on how the Army drives for results, my key takeaway is the importance of balancing short-term results with longer term strategic goals, because achieving these strategic goals will allow readiness to be sustained.

7.7 Career Ambition

I have always thought of myself as a decisive and action orientated leader, although this aligns with the Army's culture, my journey throughout this MBA has challenged me to slow down and think critically. The Methodology Chapter was particularly difficult because it pushed me outside of my comfort zone. I found a new interest in philosophy during this period, which challenged me to engage with abstract concepts and questioning the "why." I feel that this has helped me grow professionally and personally. I plan to continue exploring philosophy as a hobby and think it will also act as a tool to enhance my leadership thinking. This process has made me evaluate situations from a more strategic perspective, which is an essential trait for future promotions. Completing this MBA has highlighted to me that strong leadership is not just about making

decisions, it is about understanding people, understanding systems, understanding strategy and acting in a way that carefully balances the needs of them all.

7.8 Summary

This chapter has helped me think differently about leadership. The whole MBA process has adjusted the way I analyse and approach different situations. Using Kolb's Learning Cycle, I reflected on how I applied leadership and operational readiness frameworks during a live, large-scale deployment. My aim is to introduce some of the concepts into the Regiment with the hope that they make a difference to improve leadership practices and enhance the Regiment's operational readiness. My journey throughout this MBA has felt like a rollercoaster at times. I have embraced the highs, and the lows have challenged my academic abilities. Completing this MBA has enhanced my leadership and management skills and has contributed to continued personal and professional development. I am extremely proud of my achievement.

Glossary

Part 1: Acronyms and Abbreviations

AH	Attack Helicopter
ALC	Army Leadership Code
APC	Army Personnel Centre
ARITC	Army Recruiting and Initial Training Command
ARRC	Allied Rapid Reaction Force
Attk	Attack
Avn	Aviation
BCT	Brigade Combat Team
BG	Battlegroup
C2	Command and Control
CGS	Chief of General Staff
CO	Commanding Officer (Commander of the Regiment)
COP	Close of Play
COS	Chief of Staff
DCGS	Deputy Chief of General Staff
DDH	Defence Duty Holder
Div	Division
DP	Decision Point
ES	Engineering Support
Flypro	Flying Programme
ISR	Intelligence Surveillance and Reconnaissance
ISTAR	Intelligence Surveillance Target Acquisition Reconnaissance
ITR	Individual Training Requirements
JAC	Joint Aviation Command
JDP	Joint Doctrine Publication
JSP	Joint Service Publication
LFTT	Live Firing Tactical Training
LONDIS	London District
MBA	Master of Business Administration
MOD	Ministry of Defence
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NTM	Notice to Move
NTE	Notice to Effect
OCs	Officer Commanding (Squadron Commanders)

Ops	Operations
PT	Physical Training
RAF	Royal Air Force
RC	Regional Command
REME	Royal Electrical and Mechanical Engineers
RHQ	Regimental Headquarters
RSM	Regimental Sergeant Major
Sgt	Sergeant
SJC	Standing Joint Command
Sqn	Squadron
SSM	Squadron Sergeant Major
Tps	Troops
Trg	Training
UFN	Until Further Notice
VHR	Very High Readiness
VM	Vehicle Mechanic
WHT	Weapon Handling Test

Glossary

Part 2: Definitions

Air Power *The ability to use air capabilities in and from the air, to influence the behaviour of actors and the course of events (JDP 0-01.1).*

Battlegroup *The basic combined arms manoeuvre unit is the battlegroup, organised from a combination of combat, combat support (CS) and combat service support (CSS) subunits. A battlegroup is based on the headquarters of a combat arm unit (i.e. infantry, armoured, aviation or reconnaissance) and is the basic unit of tactical manoeuvre within a formation (Headquarters Land Warfare Centre, 2014).*

Doctrine *Fundamental principles by which military forces guide their actions in support of objectives. It is authoritative but requires judgement in application (JDP 0-01.1).*

Fighting Power *The ability of the armed forces to shape, contest, and fight. Note: It represents three interrelated components: the moral, conceptual and physical (JDP 0-01.1).*

Logistic Support *The activity to sustain forces through the provision of materiel. Note: Logistic support includes acquisition, control and distribution; provision of movement personnel and materiel and the provision of logistic support services (JDP 0-01.1).*

Mission Command *Mission Command is the British Army's command philosophy. This is an approach which empowers subordinate commanders and promotes initiative as well as freedom and speed of action. Critically, it focuses on achievement of higher intent through mission type orders. It empowers leaders at every level and is intended to generate agility and tempo (ADP Land Ops 2016).*

Operation *A sequence of coordinated actions with a defined purpose (JDP 0-01.1).*

Operational Domain *A specified sphere of capabilities and activities that can be applied within an engagement space. Note: The UK recognises the five operational domains to be: maritime, land, air, space, and cyber and electromagnetic (JDP 0-01.1).*

Readiness *The period measured from an initiation order to the moment when the headquarters or unit is ready to perform its task from its peacetime location (permanent or forward deployed) or ready for deployment (JDP 0-01.1).*

Sustainability *The ability of a force to maintain the necessary level of combat power for the duration required to achieve its objectives (JDP 0-01.1).*

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Appendix 1: Semi-Structured Interview Guide

Serial	Question	Remarks
1	How long have you served in the Army?	Icebreaker question to create a comfortable environment. This question also provides demographic and background information which will be used for framing responses.
2	What is your current role and how long have you served in it?	
3	How would you describe the leadership within the Regiment?	Content questions that address the theme of the research project. These questions capture the participants personal experiences and perspectives.
4	In your experience, how do leaders influence personnel readiness within the Regiment?	
5	In your experience, how do leaders influence training readiness within the Regiment?	
6	In your experience, how do leaders influence equipment readiness within the Regiment?	
7	What style of leadership do you think is most suitable for establishing and maintaining operational readiness as a whole?	
8	What challenges do you think leaders face in maintaining operational readiness?	Exploring questions to clarify and expand on initial responses.
9	In your opinion, what changes in leadership could enhance the Regiment's operational readiness?	
10	Do you feel this interview has captured your perspective accurately?	Cool off and closing questions to make the participant feel valued and heard.
11	Is there anything else you would like to add that has not been discussed?	
As required	That's interesting... Tell me more about... What do you mean by... Can you describe...	Probing questions to gain depth and clarity.

Appendix 2: Commanding Officer's Letter of Direction

OFFICIAL [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]
Commanding Officer
3 Regiment Army Air Corps
Wattisham Airfield
Ipswich
SUFFOLK
IP7 7RA

Email: [REDACTED]

Date: 19 Feb 25

Dear OCs

COMMANDING OFFICER'S DIRECTION AHEAD OF [REDACTED]

1. The Regiment is nearing validation on [REDACTED] and is firmly in the process of preparing for the Battlegroup's deployment to [REDACTED] on [REDACTED]. This is a busy period and there are multiple demands on our output that can, at times, work in opposition to each other. Given the little time we have available between now and our exercises, this letter attempts to provide some clarity on my intent and priorities for work. The goal is to align the Regiment on its activity over the next 2 months in order that time available is maximised and the conditions set for success on [REDACTED].

2. My priorities until deployment are:

1. DELIVER aircrew competency.
2. PREPARE for [REDACTED]
3. SUSTAIN and, where not in contradiction to Priority 1, ENHANCE readiness.

Common to all is the requirement to PROTECT our workforce.

3. Focusing our efforts on aircrew training (Priority 1) is essential if we are to deploy and operate in the way we want to fight. I recognise that we have an overall lower level of experience in our aircrew today than over the last decade; striving to build their competency is a key mitigation against the risks of operating during [REDACTED]. To achieve this, the Regiment must align to the task of maximising aircraft and aircrew availability. It will require a team effort. Whether focused on delivering flying or on delivering broader aspects of readiness (fleet management or physical instruction for instance), we will need to remain flexible, be proactive and unify against the core task. This will include support to weekend flying if required to generate additional training opportunities.

4. Where individuals and teams are not engaged on tasks relating to Priority 1, they are to prepare for [REDACTED] (Priority 2). Key staff will be required to conduct detailed planning, and we must endeavour to prepare the Regiment physically and mentally. This is intended to set the conditions for success throughout the exercise.

5. Our focus on flying over the coming months does not mean that we should abandon our drive for readiness; sustaining the momentum generated over the last 12-18 months in terms of equipment and personnel preparation for warfighting is essential (Priority 3). We will therefore need to be agile in our approach, seeking to achieve key training requirements such as ITRs in a focused and intelligent way. This may be less efficient in some circumstances, but we must avoid scale-A events that we know to be detrimental to flying output. You will need to identify personnel who are essential for flying productivity and maximise their time focused on their primary task. This

Page 1 of 2

OFFICIAL [REDACTED]

direction accepts that we will adopt a risk-based approach owned by RHQ; the BG COS will identify and track the risks that result from deprioritising readiness or routine activities. I accept that readiness capability may fall in the short term; we need to accept that this is simply a consequence of our prioritisation over this period and use risk management to guide our decisions.

6. Finally, I need you to ensure that our people understand the reasons for this approach. Please take the time to explain why they may need to refocus activity, or potentially work a little harder ahead of a major exercise. Our people are our vital ground; we must endeavour to protect our workforce and maintain morale to sustain our capability over the longer term.

[REDACTED]

Lt Col

[REDACTED]

3 AAC
CO

Distribution:

[REDACTED]

Copies to:

[REDACTED]

Appendix 3: Operations Officer's Direction

From: [REDACTED]
Sent: Monday, February 24, 2025 1:21 PM
To: [REDACTED]
Cc: [REDACTED]
Subject: Regimental Priorities to [REDACTED]
Importance: High

OFFICIAL-[REDACTED]

Sirs, All,

BLUF : 3 Regiment's Main Effort is producing competent aircrew to deploy on [REDACTED]

As you are well aware there is going to be an increasing strain over the coming weeks between flying activity and other activities we are mandated to do by the Army. As a result of the increased ask on aircrew and ES, the Regiment are having to make some difficult decisions in order to meet the start state for [REDACTED]. We must be ruthlessly efficient to achieve the ask of deploying the whole regiment to [REDACTED]. Please see below the formal direction from RHQ.

1. We will be going back to a Regimental Flypro Coord every Thursday at 1500 to plan out the flying for the following week. I expect a Flight Commander, Sqn Ops and ES representative to attend. It will be chaired by myself or someone else from RHQ. Just like pre [REDACTED] if the flight commanders could plan what they want to fly on the planning tile we will then resource it during the Coord. (invite to follow)
2. Weekend flying will be a thing. If we start to fall behind on the 75 hours we need to fly a week we will fly on Saturdays. The DP for this will be on the Flypro coord for the following week.
3. Any output that will reduce flying output is to cease unless approved by the chain of command. Any trawls that come through from the BCT will require DDH approval before being selected. Any other courses that individuals are booked on will require the approval of OCs.
4. All aircrew will be taken off Station Orderly Officer and Orderly Sgt until post [REDACTED]. The Adjutant is writing up formal direction and will be pushed out the 2ICs and SSMs by COP today.
5. Mandatory PT will be limited to COs PT. All other PT sessions will be conducted in the individuals own time or at the discretion from Sqn OCs.
6. All ITR battle camps will be cancelled UFN. Safety critical ITRs such as WHTs and Heat illness training will be prioritised.
7. Weapon cleaning will go from every two weeks to every quarter.
8. LFTT for all ES on readiness will be held at risk.
9. Aircrew involvement on [REDACTED] will be reduced to an utter minimum.

Whilst I know there are some unpalatable decisions that have been made here, please make the point when briefing downwards that these measures are only temporary until the deployment to [REDACTED]. If there are any questions or points that need clarification, please get back to me in the first instance.

Kind Regards,

[REDACTED]

OFFICIAL-[REDACTED]

Appendix 4: NVivo Preliminary Coding

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Training Readiness	8	34	17/02/2025 19:51	SJH	06/03/2025 22:35	SJH
Equipment Readiness	6	18	17/02/2025 19:56	SJH	05/03/2025 20:59	SJH
Personnel Readiness	7	16	17/02/2025 19:42	SJH	06/03/2025 22:29	SJH
Army Leadership Code	6	13	13/02/2025 21:17	SJH	06/03/2025 22:39	SJH
Communication	5	12	17/02/2025 20:06	SJH	06/03/2025 22:37	SJH
Transformational	5	11	13/02/2025 21:19	SJH	05/03/2025 21:33	SJH
Vision	5	11	17/02/2025 19:54	SJH	06/03/2025 22:29	SJH
General Leadership	5	9	13/02/2025 21:26	SJH	06/03/2025 22:42	SJH
Morale	5	8	26/02/2025 19:21	SJH	06/03/2025 22:40	SJH
Servant	3	6	13/02/2025 21:20	SJH	05/03/2025 21:30	SJH
Empowerment	4	6	17/02/2025 19:30	SJH	05/03/2025 21:15	SJH
Mission Command	4	6	17/02/2025 20:20	SJH	05/03/2025 20:57	SJH
Risk	3	6	17/02/2025 20:34	SJH	26/02/2025 20:46	SJH
Tempo	5	6	17/02/2025 20:39	SJH	05/03/2025 21:16	SJH
Laissez-faire	3	5	13/02/2025 21:24	SJH	05/03/2025 21:35	SJH
KSEB	4	5	17/02/2025 19:58	SJH	06/03/2025 22:30	SJH
Bureaucracy	3	5	25/02/2025 20:09	SJH	26/02/2025 20:45	SJH
Transactional	4	5	25/02/2025 20:21	SJH	06/03/2025 22:39	SJH
Management	3	5	26/02/2025 19:23	SJH	05/03/2025 21:31	SJH
Sustainability	3	4	17/02/2025 20:37	SJH	06/03/2025 22:38	SJH
Workforce	4	4	17/02/2025 20:38	SJH	05/03/2025 21:01	SJH
Operational Readiness	1	4	26/02/2025 19:14	SJH	26/02/2025 20:10	SJH
Development	3	3	17/02/2025 19:32	SJH	26/02/2025 20:18	SJH
High Performance	1	3	17/02/2025 19:44	SJH	17/02/2025 20:13	SJH
Aircraft	2	3	17/02/2025 20:31	SJH	05/03/2025 21:27	SJH
Vehicles	2	3	17/02/2025 20:31	SJH	05/03/2025 20:58	SJH
Toxic Leadership	2	3	17/02/2025 20:41	SJH	26/02/2025 20:22	SJH
Lessons ID	3	3	25/02/2025 20:13	SJH	05/03/2025 21:29	SJH
Battlefield	1	3	26/02/2025 19:48	SJH	26/02/2025 19:49	SJH
Safety	2	2	17/02/2025 20:09	SJH	26/02/2025 20:10	SJH
Collaborative Leadership	1	2	25/02/2025 19:52	SJH	25/02/2025 19:56	SJH
Direction	2	2	26/02/2025 20:05	SJH	05/03/2025 21:22	SJH
Teamwork	1	1	25/02/2025 19:58	SJH	25/02/2025 19:58	SJH
Survivability	1	1	26/02/2025 19:51	SJH	26/02/2025 19:51	SJH

Appendix 5: British Army Command Structure¹

CGS. *The Chief of General Staff is the head of the British Army and reports direct to the Chief of Defence Staff.*

DCGS. *The Deputy Chief of Defence Staff oversees Army policies, budgets and maintains operational oversight.*

Army HQ. *The British Army's most senior headquarters and is led by the Chief of General Staff.*

Field Army. *Field Army is responsible for force generating and deploying land forces for operations and deterrence.*

HQ ARRC. *Headquarters Allied Rapid Reaction Corps is NATO's high readiness Headquarters and leads the NATO Response Force.*

JAC. *Joint Aviation Command is responsible for training, sustaining, assuring and delivering battlefield aviation capabilities to operations.*

1 Avn BCT. *The 1st Aviation Brigade Combat Team commands and sustains Army aviation for rapid response and warfighting.*

Attk Avn Regt. *Attack Aviation Regiments specialise in attack aviation with Apache AH-64E helicopters.*

¹ Future Soldier: Transforming the British Army (MOD, 2021)